

A METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF COBALT IN PRESENCE OF NICKEL.

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The solubility of the greenish yellow precipitate of nickel *isonitrosothiocamphor* in dilute hydrochloric acid solution and the insolubility of the cobalt complex in the same solvent have been utilised in estimating cobalt in presence of nickel.

The possibility of the use of *di-isonitrosothiocamphor* as an indicator in alkalimetry has already been reported (Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 752). *l-isoNitrosothiocamphor*, prepared from *l-thiocamphor*, can also be used for the same purpose and the p_H range in both cases has been found to be between 8.6-9. In this connexion the author studied the effects of various metallic salts on 1% alcoholic *isonitrosothiocamphors*. An ammoniacal solution of the reagent was found to be very sensitive in the case of copper and cobalt giving brown and red colouration with sensitiveness of 1:4,50,000 and 1:50,000 respectively. The reagent was found to be without any effect on salts of iron, aluminium, chromium, zinc, magnesium, manganese and barium.

The solubility of the greenish yellow precipitate of nickel *isonitrosothiocamphor* in dilute hydrochloric acid and the insolubility of the cobalt complex in the same solvent has been utilised for the quantitative estimation of cobalt in presence of nickel. The cobalt salt has been found to possess the formula $C_{30}H_{42}O_3N_3S_3Co$, and is represented as

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

For the purpose of estimating cobalt, when present alone, the solution containing not more than 0.01 g.-0.04 g. of cobalt was diluted to 200 c.c. with water and heated to boiling. 50 c.c. of 10% sodium acetate solution were added followed by an 1% alcoholic solution of *isonitrosothiocamphor* till there was no further precipitation. The mixture was thoroughly stirred and the scarlet-red precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed with hot water to remove sodium acetate, then with $N/5-NaOH$ to remove any excess of the reagent. It was then

washed with 2*N*-HCl and finally once again with hot water. It was then dried at 105°-110° and weighed.

The precipitate can also be collected on a filter paper, washed with hot water, ignited and finally weighed as cobalt sulphate.

In presence of nickel, the same procedure was followed except that 30 c.c. of 2*N*-HCl were added after the precipitation and the mixture allowed to stand for 30-40 minutes at room temperature before filtering.

Ni taken.	Co taken.	Wt. of cobaltic complex found.	Weight of isonitroso-thiocampher method (I)	Cobalt found by Ignition to CoSO ₄ .
—	0·02059 g.	0·2252 g.	0·02054g.	0·2052 g
—	0·02059	0·2261	0·02062	0·2063
—	0·02059	0·2256	0·02057	—
—	0·0103	0·1133	0·01033	0·1032
—	0·0103	0·1127	0·01028	0·1032
—	0·0103	0·1125	0·01026	—
0·00993 g.	0·0206	0·2262	0·02063	—
0·01985	0·0206	0·2264	0·02065	0·02067
0·0397	0·0206	0·2256	0·02057	—
0·00993	0·0103	0·1127	0·01028	0·01036
0·01985	0·0103	0·1132	0·01032	0·01039

A solution of chemically pure salt of known concentration was used as the standard.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The present reagent has got certain advantages over others. *o*-Nitroso β -naphthol (Hinsky and Knorre, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 699; Knorre, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1893, 26, 246) being sensitive to light cannot be preserved for a long time and it is difficult to obtain a directly weighable precipitate with this. Rubenic acid (Ray and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 118) also does not give a directly weighable precipitate of cobalt and does not permit of its separation from nickel. The molecular weight of the isonitrosothiocampher cobalt complex is very high giving about 9% Co.

Experiments are in progress for the estimation of cobalt by colorimetric and micro methods with the help of this reagent.

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